

The Elliptic Curves $y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ over \mathbf{F}_p

Ahmet Tekcan

Abstract—Let p be a prime number, \mathbf{F}_p be a finite field and $t \in \mathbf{F}_p^* = \mathbf{F}_p - \{0\}$. In this paper we obtain some properties of elliptic curves $E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ over \mathbf{F}_p . In the first section we give some notations and preliminaries from elliptic curves. In the second section we consider the rational points (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$. We give a formula for the number of rational points on $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p^n for an integer $n \geq 1$. We also give some formulas for the sum of x - and y -coordinates of the points (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$. In the third section we consider the rank of $E_t : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ and its 2-isogenous curve \bar{E}_t over \mathbf{Q} . We proved that the rank of E_t and \bar{E}_t is 2 over \mathbf{Q} . In the last section we obtain some formulas for the sums $\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n$ for an integer $n \geq 1$, where $a_{p,t}$ denote the trace of Frobenius.

Keywords—elliptic curves over finite fields, rational points on elliptic curves, rank, trace of Frobenius.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mordell began his famous paper [13] with the words *Mathematicians have been familiar with very few questions for so long a period with so little accomplished in the way of general results, as that of finding the rational points on elliptic curves*. The history of elliptic curves is a long one, and exciting applications for elliptic curves continue to be discovered. Recently, important and useful applications of elliptic curves have been found for cryptography [6,11,12], for factoring large integers [9], and for primality proving [1,5]. The mathematical theory of elliptic curves was also crucial in the proof of Fermat's Last Theorem [19].

Let q be a positive integer, \mathbf{F}_q be a finite field and let $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_q$ denote the algebraic closure of \mathbf{F}_q with $\text{char}(\bar{\mathbf{F}}_q) \neq 2, 3$. An elliptic curve E over \mathbf{F}_q is defined by an equation

$$E_{q,a,b} : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b,$$

where $a, b \in \mathbf{F}_q$ and $4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$. We can view an elliptic curve $E_{q,a,b}$ as a curve in projective plane \mathbf{P}^2 , with a homogeneous equation $y^2z = x^3 + axz^2 + bz^3$, and one point at infinity, namely $(0, 1, 0)$. This point ∞ is the point where all vertical lines meet. We denote this point by O . Let

$$E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbf{F}_q \times \mathbf{F}_q : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b\} \cup \{O\}$$

denote the set of rational points (x, y) on $E_{q,a,b}$. Then it is a subgroup of $E_{q,a,b}$. The order of $E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q)$, denoted by $\#E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q)$, is defined as the number of the rational points on $E_{q,a,b}$ (for further details see [15,17,18]), and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \#E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q) &= 1 + \sum_{x \in \mathbf{F}_q} \left(1 + \frac{x^3 + ax + b}{\mathbf{F}_q} \right) \quad (1) \\ &= q + 1 + \sum_{x \in \mathbf{F}_q} \left(\frac{x^3 + ax + b}{\mathbf{F}_q} \right), \end{aligned}$$

Ahmet Tekcan is with the Uludag University, Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, Bursa-TURKEY, email: tekcan@uludag.edu.tr, <http://matematik.uludag.edu.tr/AhmetTekcan.htm>.

where $\left(\frac{\cdot}{\mathbf{F}_q}\right)$ denotes the Legendre symbol.

Let

$$\#E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q) = q + 1 - a_{q,a,b}. \quad (2)$$

Then $a_{q,a,b}$ is called the trace of Frobenius and satisfies the inequality

$$|a_{q,a,b}| \leq 2\sqrt{q}$$

known as the Hasse interval [18, p.91]. The formula (1) can be generalized to any field \mathbf{F}_{q^n} for an integer $n \geq 2$ [18, p.97]. Let $\#E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_q) = q + 1 - a_{q,a,b}$ and let

$$X^2 - a_{q,a,b}X + q = (X - \alpha)(X - \beta). \quad (3)$$

Then the order of $E_{q,a,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_{q^n} is

$$\#E_{q,a,b}(\mathbf{F}_{q^n}) = q^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n). \quad (4)$$

II. RATIONAL POINTS ON ELLIPTIC CURVES

$$E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x \text{ OVER } \mathbf{F}_p.$$

In [16], we consider the elliptic curves $E_{p,\lambda} : y^2 = x(x-\lambda)(x-\lambda)$ over \mathbf{F}_p for $\lambda \neq 0, 1$, where p is a prime number and \mathbf{F}_p is a finite field. We consider the rational points on $E_{p,\lambda}$ and also its rank over \mathbf{Q} . In the present paper we consider the elliptic curves

$$E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x \quad (5)$$

over \mathbf{F}_p for an integer $t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. This elliptic curve was studied by Lemmermeyer and Mollin [8] in the sense of its Tate-Shafarevich group. Here we only consider its rational points, rank and trace of Frobenius.

Let Q_p denote the set of quadratic residues. Let $Q_p^{4,+}$ denote the set of 4th power of elements of \mathbf{F}_p^* and let $Q_p^{4,-} = \mathbf{F}_p^* - Q_p^{4,+}$. Set $Q_p^4 = Q_p^{4,+} \cup Q_p^{4,-}$. Then $\#Q_p^{4,+} = \#Q_p^{4,-} = \frac{p-1}{4}$ and $\#Q_p^4 = \frac{p-1}{2}$. Recall that the order of $E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ over \mathbf{F}_p is given in [18, p.105] by

1. If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1$.
2. If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, write $p = a^2 + b^2$, where a and b are integers with b is even and $a + b \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \begin{cases} p + 1 - 2a & \text{if } k \in Q_p^{4,+} \\ p + 1 + 2a & \text{if } k \in Q_p^{4,-} \\ p + 1 \pm 2b & \text{if } k \notin Q_p. \end{cases}$$

First we generalize this result to any field \mathbf{F}_{p^n} for an integer $n \geq 2$.

Theorem 2.1: Let $E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_p .

- 1) If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = \begin{cases} (p^{\frac{n}{2}} - 1)^2 & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ p^n + 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 1, 3 \pmod{4} \\ (p^{\frac{n}{2}} + 1)^2 & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

2) If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 -$

$$\begin{cases} (a+ib)^n + (a-ib)^n & \text{if } t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+} \\ (-a+ib)^n + (-a-ib)^n & \text{if } t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}. \end{cases}$$

Proof: 1. Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1$. Hence $a_{p,t} = 0$ by (2). Let

$$X^2 + p = (X - \alpha)(X - \beta)$$

for $\alpha = i\sqrt{p}$ and $\beta = -i\sqrt{p}$ by (3).

Let $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, i.e. $n = 4m$ for an integer $m \geq 1$. Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^{4m} + (-i\sqrt{p})^{4m} \\ &= i^{4m}(\sqrt{p})^{4m} + (-i)^{4m}(\sqrt{p})^{4m} \\ &= p^{2m} + p^{2m} \\ &= 2p^{2m} \\ &= 2p^{\frac{n}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) = p^n + 1 - 2p^{\frac{n}{2}} = (p^{\frac{n}{2}} - 1)^2$ by (4).

Let $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 1 + 4m$. Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^n + (-i\sqrt{p})^n \\ &= i^{4m+1}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+1} + (-i)^{4m+1}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+1} \\ &= i(\sqrt{p})^{4m+1} + (-i)(\sqrt{p})^{4m+1} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) = p^n + 1$.

Let $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 2 + 4m$. Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^n + (-i\sqrt{p})^n \\ &= i^{4m+2}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+2} + (-i)^{4m+2}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+2} \\ &= (-1)p^{2m+1} + (-1)p^{2m+1} \\ &= -2p^{2m+1} \\ &= -2p^{\frac{n}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) = p^n + 1 + 2p^{\frac{n}{2}} = (p^{\frac{n}{2}} + 1)^2$.

Finally, let $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 3 + 4m$. Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^n + (-i\sqrt{p})^n \\ &= i^{4m+3}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+3} + (-i)^{4m+3}(\sqrt{p})^{4m+3} \\ &= (-i)(\sqrt{p})^{4m+3} + i(\sqrt{p})^{4m+3} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) = p^n + 1$.

2. Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and let $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$. Then $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1 - 2a$ and hence $a_{p,t} = 2a$ by (2). Let

$$\begin{aligned} X^2 - 2aX + p &= (X - \alpha)(X - \beta) \\ &= X^2 - X(\alpha + \beta) + \alpha\beta. \end{aligned}$$

Then $2a = \alpha + \beta$ and $p = \alpha\beta$. Hence we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2a = \alpha + \frac{p}{\alpha} &\Leftrightarrow \alpha^2 - 2a\alpha + p = 0 \\ &\Leftrightarrow \alpha_{1,2} = \frac{2a \pm \sqrt{4a^2 - 4p}}{2} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \alpha_{1,2} = a \pm ib. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\alpha_1 = a + ib \Rightarrow \beta_1 = \frac{p}{\alpha_1} = a - ib$$

or

$$\alpha_2 = a - ib \Rightarrow \beta_2 = \frac{p}{\alpha_2} = a + ib.$$

Consequently in both cases, the order of $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_{p^n} is

$$\begin{aligned} \#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) &= p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) \\ &= p^n + 1 - [(a+ib)^n + (a-ib)^n]. \end{aligned}$$

Let $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$. Then $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1 + 2a$ and hence $a_{p,t} = -2a$ by (2). Let

$$\begin{aligned} X^2 + 2aX + p &= (X - \alpha)(X - \beta) \\ &= X^2 - X(\alpha + \beta) + \alpha\beta. \end{aligned}$$

Then $-2a = \alpha + \beta$ and $p = \alpha\beta$. Hence we get

$$\begin{aligned} -2a = \alpha + \frac{p}{\alpha} &\Leftrightarrow \alpha^2 + 2a\alpha + p = 0 \\ &\Leftrightarrow \alpha_{1,2} = \frac{-2a \pm \sqrt{4a^2 - 4p}}{2} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \alpha_{1,2} = -a \pm ib. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\alpha_1 = -a + ib \Rightarrow \beta_1 = \frac{p}{\alpha_1} = -a - ib$$

or

$$\alpha_2 = -a - ib \Rightarrow \beta_2 = \frac{p}{\alpha_2} = -a + ib.$$

Consequently the order of $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_{p^n} is

$$\begin{aligned} \#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) &= p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) \\ &= p^n + 1 - [(-a+ib)^n + (-a-ib)^n]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. ■

In the following table some values of p, a and b is given.

p	a	b	p	a	b
5	1	2	229	15	2
13	3	2	233	13	8
17	1	4	241	15	4
29	5	2	257	1	16
37	1	6	269	13	10
41	5	4	277	9	14
53	7	2	281	5	16
61	5	6	293	17	2
73	3	8	313	13	12
89	5	8	317	11	14
97	9	4	337	9	16
101	1	10	349	5	18
109	3	10	353	17	8
113	7	8	373	7	18
137	11	4	389	17	10
149	7	10	397	19	6
157	11	6	401	1	20
173	13	2	409	3	20
181	9	10	421	15	14
193	7	12	433	17	12
197	1	14	449	7	20

In the following examples the orders of $E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ over \mathbf{F}_{p^n} are given for $2 \leq n \leq 15$.

Example 2.1: Let $p = 23$ and $t = 2$. Then the order of $E_{23,2} : y^2 = x^3 - 4x$ over \mathbf{F}_{23^n} is

n	\mathbf{F}_{23^n}
2	576
3	12168
4	278784
5	6436344
6	148060224
7	3404825448
8	78310425600
9	1801152661464
10	41426524086336
11	952809757913928
12	21914624135948544
13	504036361936467384
14	11592836331348400704
15	266635235464391245608

Example 2.2: Let $p = 13$. Then $a = 3$ and $b = 2$. Let $t = 4$. Then $t^2 \equiv 3 \pmod{13}$. So $t^2 \in Q_{13}^{4,+} = \{1, 3, 9\}$. Then the order of $E_{13,4} : y^2 = x^3 - 3x$ over \mathbf{F}_{13^n} is

n	\mathbf{F}_{13^n}
2	160
3	2216
4	28800
5	372488
6	4830880
7	62757416
8	815731200
9	10604386564
10	137857808810
11	1792157762000
12	23298078210000
13	302875099300000
14	3937376432000000
15	51185893380000000

Similarly let $p = 13$ and $t = 11$. Then $t^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{13}$. So $t^2 \in Q_{13}^{4,-}$. Therefore the order of $E_{13,11} : y^2 = x^3 - 4x$ over \mathbf{F}_{13^n} is

n	\mathbf{F}_{13^n}
2	160
3	2180
4	28800
5	370100
6	4830880
7	62739620
8	815731200
9	106041612184
10	137857808810
11	1792163026000
12	23298078210000
13	302875113900000
14	3937376432000000
15	51185892640000000

Now we consider some properties of rational points on elliptic curve $E_{p,t}$.

Theorem 2.2: Let $[x]$ denote the x -coordinates of (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$. Then sum of $[x]$ on $E_{p,t}$ is

$$\sum_{[x]} E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \sum \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 - t^2x}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) .x$$

for all primes p

Proof: We know that

$$\left(\frac{x^3 - t^2x}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x^3 - t^2x \text{ is zero} \\ 1 & \text{if } x^3 - t^2x \text{ is a square} \\ -1 & \text{if } x^3 - t^2x \text{ is not a square.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\left(\frac{x^3 - t^2x}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0$. Then $x^3 - t^2x = 0$, and hence this equation has three solutions $x = 0, x = t$ and $x = -t$. Then $y^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \Leftrightarrow y \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. So for such a point x , we have a point $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,t}$. Therefore we get $(x + 0).x = x$ is added to the sum.

Let $\left(\frac{x^3 - t^2x}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$. Then $x^3 - t^2x$ is a square in \mathbf{F}_p . Let $x^3 - t^2x = k^2$ for any $k \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then $y^2 \equiv k^2 \pmod{p} \Leftrightarrow y = \pm k$, that is, for any point (x, k) on $E_{p,t}$, the point $(x, -k)$ is also on $E_{p,t}$. Therefore for each point x we have $(1 + 1).x = 2x$ is added to the sum.

Finally, let $\left(\frac{x^3 - t^2x}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1$. Then $x^3 - t^2x$ is not a square in \mathbf{F}_p . Therefore the equation $y^2 \equiv x^3 - t^2x \pmod{p}$ has no solution. Therefore for each point x , we have $(1 + (-1)).x = 0$ as we claimed. ■

Theorem 2.3: Let $[y]$ denote the y -coordinates of (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$.

1) If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then the sum of $[y]$ on $E_{p,t}$ is

$$\sum_{[y]} E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^2 - 3p}{2}.$$

2) If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then the sum of $[y]$ on $E_{p,t}$ is

$$\sum_{[y]} E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \begin{cases} \frac{p^2 - (2a+3)p}{2} & \text{if } t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+} \\ \frac{p^2 + (2a-3)p}{2} & \text{if } t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}. \end{cases}$$

Proof: 1. Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Note that the cubic equation $x^3 - t^2x = 0$ has three solutions $x = 0, x = t$ and $x = -t$. For the other values of x , we have both x and $-x$. One of these gives two points. The one makes $x^3 - t^2x$ a square. So there are two values of y since $y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ is square. Let $x^3 - t^2x = k^2$ for any $k \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then we have $y^2 = k^2$ if and only if $y = k$ and $y = -k = p - k$. So the sum of these values of y is $k + (p - k) = p$. We know that there are $\frac{p-3}{2}$ points x such that $y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ is a square. Therefore the sum of y -coordinates of all points (x, y) is

$$p \left(\frac{p-3}{2} \right) = \frac{p^2 - 3p}{2}.$$

2. Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$, then $E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1 - 2a$. We know that the cubic equation $x^3 - t^2x = 0$ has three solutions $x = 0, x = t$ and $x = -t$, that is, there are three points $(0, 0), (t, 0), (-t, 0)$ on $E_{p,t}$. The sum of y -coordinates of these points is 0. Further we have to disregard the point ∞ . Then there are $(p + 1 - 2a) - 4 = p - 2a - 3$ points (x, y) on

$E_{p,t}$ such that $y \neq 0$. Half of these points make $x^3 - t^2x$ a square, that is, there are $\frac{p-2a-3}{2}$ points x such that $x^3 - t^2x$ is a square. Let $x^3 - t^2x = k^2$ for any $k \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then we have $y^2 = k^2$ if and only if $y = k$ and $y = -k = p - k$. So the sum of these values of y is $k + (p - k) = p$. Hence the sum of y -coordinates of all points (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$ is

$$p \left(\frac{p-2a-3}{2} \right) = \frac{p^2 - (2a+3)p}{2}.$$

If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$, then $E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1 + 2a$. The cubic equation $x^3 - t^2x = 0$ has three solutions $x = 0, x = t$ and $x = -t$, that is, there are three points $(0, 0), (t, 0), (-t, 0)$ on $E_{p,t}$ and the sum of y -coordinates of these points is 0. Further we have to disregard the point ∞ . Then there are $(p + 1 + 2a) - 4 = p + 2a - 3$ points (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$ such that $y \neq 0$. Half of these points make $x^3 - t^2x$ a square, that is, there are $\frac{p+2a-3}{2}$ points x such that $x^3 - t^2x$ is a square. Let $x^3 - t^2x = k^2$ for any $k \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then we have $y^2 = k^2$ if and only if $y = k$ and $y = -k = p - k$. So the sum of these values of y is $k + (p - k) = p$. Hence the sum of y -coordinates of all points (x, y) on $E_{p,t}$ is

$$p \left(\frac{p+2a-3}{2} \right) = \frac{p^2 + (2a-3)p}{2}.$$

Theorem 2.4: Let $\mathbf{E}_{p,t} = \{E_{p,t} : t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*\}$ denote the set of all elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p . Then

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} \#\mathbf{E}_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}$$

for all primes p .

Proof: Note that there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p . We know that the order of $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $p+1$ when $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Therefore the total number of the points (x, y) on all elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$(p+1) \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) = \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}.$$

Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$, then the order of $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $p + 1 - 2a$, and if $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$, then the order of $E_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $p + 1 + 2a$. Further the order of $Q_p^{4,+}$ and $Q_p^{4,-}$ is $\frac{p-1}{4}$. Therefore the total number of the points (x, y) on all elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{p-1}{4}(p+1-2a) + \frac{p-1}{4}(p+1+2a) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4}(p+1-2a+p+1+2a) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4}(2p+2) \\ &= \frac{p^2-1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

as we claimed. ■

Theorem 2.5: The sum of $[y]$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p)$ is

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} \mathbf{E}_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^3 - 4p^2 + 3p}{4}$$

for all primes p .

Proof: Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. We know that the sum of $[y]$ is $\frac{p^2-3p}{2}$. Further there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ elliptic curves in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}$. Therefore the sum of $[y]$ of all points (x, y) on all elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p)$ is

$$\left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{p^2-3p}{2} \right) = \frac{p^3 - 4p^2 + 3p}{4}.$$

Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. We know that there are $\frac{p-1}{4}$ elements in both $Q_p^{4,+}$ and $Q_p^{4,-}$. Further by Theorem 2.3, if $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$, then the sum of $[y]$ of all points on elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ is $\frac{p^2-(2a+3)p}{2}$, and if $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$, then the sum of $[y]$ of all points on elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ is $\frac{p^2+(2a-3)p}{2}$. Therefore the sum of $[y]$ of all points on elliptic curves $E_{p,t}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{p-1}{4} \right) \left[\frac{p^2 - (2a+3)p}{2} + \frac{p^2 + (2a-3)p}{2} \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{p-1}{4} \right) \left(\frac{2p^2 - 6p}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{p^3 - 4p^2 + 3p}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

■

III. RANK OF $E_t : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ OVER \mathbf{Q} .

Let E be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{Q} . By Mordell's theorem, we know that $E(\mathbf{Q})$ is a finitely generated abelian group, that is, $E(\mathbf{Q}) = E(\mathbf{Q})_{tors} \times \mathbf{Z}^r$. Further by Mazur's theorem,

$$E(\mathbf{Q})_{tors} \cong \mathbf{Z}/n\mathbf{Z} \text{ for } 1 \leq n \leq 10 \text{ or } n = 12$$

or

$$E(\mathbf{Q})_{tors} \cong \mathbf{Z}/2\mathbf{Z} \times \mathbf{Z}/2n\mathbf{Z} \text{ for } 1 \leq n \leq 4.$$

On the other hand, it is not known that what values of rank r are possible for elliptic curves over \mathbf{Q} . The main idea is that a rank can be arbitrary large. The current record is an example of elliptic curve with rank ≥ 28 , found by Elkies [3] in 2006. The previous record one with rank ≥ 24 , found by Martin and McMillen [10] in 2000. The highest rank of an elliptic curve which is known exactly (not only a lower bound for rank) is equal to 18, and it was found by Elkies [3] in 2006. It improves previous records due to Kretschmer [7](rank = 10), Schneiders-Zimmer [14](rank = 11), Fermigier [4](rank = 14), Dujella [2](rank = 15) and Elkies [3](rank = 17).

Recall that the 2-isogenous curve of an elliptic curve

$$E_{a,b} : y^2 = x^3 + ax^2 + bx$$

is given by

$$\bar{E}_{a,b} : y^2 = x^3 + \bar{a}x^2 + \bar{b}x, \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{a} = -2a$ and $\bar{b} = a^2 - 4b$. Then there exists a 2-isogeny ϕ from $E_{a,b}$ to $\bar{E}_{a,b}$ given by

$$\phi : E_{a,b} \rightarrow \bar{E}_{a,b}, \quad \phi(x, y) = \left(\frac{y^2}{x^2}, \frac{y(b-x^2)}{x^2} \right).$$

Conversely, there exists a dual isogeny ψ from $\overline{E}_{a,b}$ to $E_{a,b}$ given by

$$\psi : \overline{E}_{a,b} \rightarrow E_{a,b}, \quad \psi(x, y) = \left(\frac{y^2}{4x^2}, \frac{y(a^2 - 4b - x^2)}{8x^2} \right).$$

Let

$$2^r = \frac{\#\alpha(E_{a,b}(\mathbf{Q}))\#\overline{\alpha}(\overline{E}_{a,b}(\mathbf{Q}))}{4}, \quad (7)$$

where α is a homomorphism

$$\alpha : E_{a,b}(\mathbf{Q}) \rightarrow \mathbf{Q}^*/\mathbf{Q}^{*2}$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\rightarrow 1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}} \\ (0, 0) &\rightarrow b \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}} \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow x \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{Q}^* is the multiplicative group of rational units, and \mathbf{Q}^{*2} is the subgroup consisting of perfect squares. So $\mathbf{Q}^*/\mathbf{Q}^{*2}$ is like the non-zero rational numbers, with two elements identified if their quotient is the square of a rational number. We shall call α the Weil map (in fact it is actually a group homomorphism). We found the Weil map from the group of rational points on $E_{a,b}$ to the group $\mathbf{Q}^*/\mathbf{Q}^{*2}$ by studying the rational points on torsors

$$T^{(\psi)}(b_1) : N^2 = b_1M^4 + aM^2e^2 + b_2e^4, \quad (8)$$

where b_1 runs through the square free divisors of $b = b_1b_2$. Then $\alpha(E_{a,b}(\mathbf{Q}))$ consists of $b \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}$, together with those $b_1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}$ such that (8) has a solution (N, M, e) .

Similarly, $\overline{\alpha}$ is an Weil map, which is from the group of rational points on $\overline{E}_{a,b}$ to the group $\mathbf{Q}^*/\mathbf{Q}^{*2}$ by studying the rational points on torsors

$$T^{(\phi)}(\overline{b}_1) : N^2 = \overline{b}_1M^4 + \overline{a}M^2e^2 + \overline{b}_2e^4, \quad (9)$$

where \overline{b}_1 runs through the square free divisors of $\overline{b} = \overline{b}_1\overline{b}_2$. Then $\overline{\alpha}(\overline{E}_{a,b}(\mathbf{Q}))$ consists of $\overline{b} \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}$, together with those $\overline{b}_1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}$ such that (9) has a solution (N, M, e) .

Note that the 2-isogenous curve of our curve $E_t : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ is

$$\overline{E}_t : y^2 = x^3 + 4t^2x \quad (10)$$

if t is odd, or

$$\overline{E}_t : y^2 = x^3 + \frac{t^2}{4}x \quad (11)$$

if t is even by (6). Now we can consider the rank of E_t and \overline{E}_t over \mathbf{Q} .

Theorem 3.1: The rank of E_t and \overline{E}_t over \mathbf{Q} is 2.

Proof: Elliptic curves with a rational point of order 2 like our curves $E_t : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ come attached with a 2-isogeny $\phi : E_t \rightarrow \overline{E}_t$ (depending of choice of point if E_t has three rational points of order 2) as we mentioned above.

Now consider the our elliptic curve $E_t : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$. Then there are four possibilities for $b_1 = -t^2$ which are ± 1 and $\pm t$.

If $b_1 = 1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = M^4 - t^2e^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (t^2, t, 0)$. If $b_1 = -1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -M^4 + t^2e^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (t, 0, -1)$. If $b_1 = t$, then the equation

$$N^2 = tM^4 - te^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (0, t^2, t^2)$ and if $b_1 = -t$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -tM^4 + te^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (0, t^2, -t^2)$. So

$$\alpha(E_t(\mathbf{Q})) = \{\pm 1, \pm t \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}\} \text{ and } \# \alpha(E_t(\mathbf{Q})) = 4 \quad (12)$$

by (8).

Now we consider the 2-isogeny of E_t . If t is odd, then the 2-isogenous curve of E_t is $\overline{E}_t : y^2 = x^3 + 4t^2x$ by (10). Then there are four possibilities for $\overline{b}_1 = 4t^2$ which are ± 1 and $\pm 2t$.

If $\overline{b}_1 = 1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = M^4 + 4t^2e^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (2t, 0, 1)$. If $\overline{b}_1 = -1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -M^4 - 4t^2e^4$$

has no solution (N, M, e) since its right-hand side is strictly negative. If $\overline{b}_1 = 2t$, then the equation

$$N^2 = 2tM^4 + 2te^4$$

has no solution (N, M, e) and if $\overline{b}_1 = -2t$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -2tM^4 - 2te^4$$

has no solution (N, M, e) since its right-hand side is strictly negative. Hence

$$\overline{\alpha}(\overline{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = \{1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}\} \text{ and } \# \overline{\alpha}(\overline{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = 1$$

by (9).

If t is even, then the 2-isogenous curve of E_t is $\overline{E}_t : y^2 = x^3 + \frac{t^2}{4}x$ by (11). Let $t = 2k$ for integers $k \geq 1$. Then \overline{E}_t becomes an elliptic curve has the form $\overline{E}_t : y^2 = x^3 + k^2x$. Then there are four possibilities for $\overline{b}_1 = k^2$ which are ± 1 and $\pm k$.

If $\overline{b}_1 = 1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = M^4 + k^2e^4$$

has a solution $(N, M, e) = (k, 0, 1)$. If $\overline{b}_1 = -1$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -M^4 - k^2e^4$$

has no solution (N, M, e) since its right-hand side is strictly negative. If $\overline{b}_1 = k$, then the equation

$$N^2 = kM^4 + ke^4$$

has no solution and if $\bar{b}_1 = -k$, then the equation

$$N^2 = -kM^4 - ke^4$$

has no solution since its right-hand side is strictly negative. Hence

$$\bar{\alpha}(\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = \{1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}\} \text{ and } \#\bar{\alpha}(\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = 1$$

by (9). So in both cases, i.e. whether t is even or odd, we have

$$\bar{\alpha}(\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = \{1 \pmod{\mathbf{Q}^{*2}}\} \text{ and } \#\bar{\alpha}(\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})) = 1 \quad (13)$$

Applying (12) and (13), we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2^r &= \frac{\#\alpha(E_t(\mathbf{Q})) \cdot \#\bar{\alpha}(\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q}))}{4} \\ &= \frac{4 \cdot 1}{4} \\ &= 4 \\ &\Leftrightarrow r = 2. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the rank of $E_t(\mathbf{Q})$ and $\bar{E}_t(\mathbf{Q})$ over \mathbf{Q} is 2 by (7) as we claimed. ■

IV. TRACE OF FROBENIUS OF ELLIPTIC CURVES

$$E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x.$$

Let $a_{p,t}$ denote the trace of Frobenius of elliptic curve $E_{p,t} : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$. Then by (2), we get $\#E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p+1 - a_{p,t}$. In this section we will obtain some relations on the sums

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n$$

for an integer $n \geq 1$.

Theorem 4.1: Let $a_{p,t}$ denote the trace of Frobenius of elliptic curve $E_{p,t}$.

1) If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n = 0$$

for all integers $n \geq 1$.

2) Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, write $p = a^2 + b^2$.

i. If $a + b \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n = 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)$$

and

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n = (-1)^n 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1).$$

ii. If $a + b \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n = (-1)^n 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)$$

and

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n = 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1).$$

for all integers $n \geq 1$.

Proof: 1. Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then $E_{p,t}(\mathbf{F}) = p+1$. So $a_{p,t} = 0$ by (2). Consequently all powers of sums of $a_{p,t} = 0$ is 0, that is

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n = 0$$

for all integers $n \geq 1$.

2. Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and let $a+b \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$, then $a_{p,t} = 2a$ and hence the sum of $a_{p,t}^n$ over $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n &= \#Q_p^{4,+} \cdot \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= \#Q_p^{4,+} \cdot (2a)^n \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4} \cdot 2^n a^n \\ &= 2^{n-2} (p-1) a^n. \end{aligned}$$

If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$, then $a_{p,t} = -2a$ and hence the sum of $a_{p,t}^n$ over $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n &= \#Q_p^{4,-} \cdot \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= \#Q_p^{4,-} \cdot (-2a)^n \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4} \cdot (-1)^n 2^n a^n \\ &= (-1)^n 2^{n-2} (p-1) a^n. \end{aligned}$$

Let $a + b \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$, then $a_{p,t} = -2a$ and hence the sum of $a_{p,t}^n$ over $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,+}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n &= \#Q_p^{4,+} \cdot \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= \#Q_p^{4,+} \cdot (-2a)^n \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4} \cdot (-1)^n 2^n a^n \\ &= (-1)^n 2^{n-2} (p-1) a^n. \end{aligned}$$

If $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$, then $a_{p,t} = 2a$ and hence the sum of $a_{p,t}^n$ over $t^2 \in Q_p^{4,-}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n &= \#Q_p^{4,-} \cdot \sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,-}} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= \#Q_p^{4,-} \cdot (2a)^n \\ &= \frac{p-1}{4} \cdot 2^n a^n \\ &= 2^{n-2} (p-1) a^n. \end{aligned}$$

Form above theorem we can give the following theorem. ■

Theorem 4.2: If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ 2^{n-1} a^n (p-1) & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

for all integers $n \geq 1$.

Proof: Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and let $a+b \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Then we know that

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^{4,+}} a_{p,t}^n = 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)$$

and

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n = (-1)^n 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1).$$

If n is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n &= \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, +} a_{p,t}^n + \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) - 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

If n is even, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n &= \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, +} a_{p,t}^n + \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) + 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) \\ &= 2(2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)) \\ &= 2^{n-1} a^n (p-1). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly let $a + b \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then we know that

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, +} a_{p,t}^n = (-1)^n 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)$$

and

$$\sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n = 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1).$$

If n is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n &= \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, +} a_{p,t}^n + \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= -2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) + 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

If n is even, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} a_{p,t}^n &= \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, +} a_{p,t}^n + \sum_{t^2 \in Q^4, -} a_{p,t}^n \\ &= 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) + 2^{n-2} a^n (p-1) \\ &= 2(2^{n-2} a^n (p-1)) \\ &= 2^{n-1} a^n (p-1). \end{aligned}$$

■

REFERENCES

- [1] A.O.L. Atkin and F. Moralin. *Elliptic Curves and Primality Proving*. Math. Comp. **61** (1993), 29–68.
- [2] A. Dujella. *An Example of Elliptic Curve over \mathbf{Q} with Rank Equal to 15*. Proc. Japan Acad. Ser. A Math. Sci. **78**(2002), 109–111.
- [3] N.D. Elkies. *Some More Rank Records: $E(\mathbf{Q}) = (\mathbf{Z}/2\mathbf{Z}) * \mathbf{Z}^{18}$, $(\mathbf{Z}/4\mathbf{Z}) * \mathbf{Z}^{12}$, $(\mathbf{Z}/8\mathbf{Z}) * \mathbf{Z}^6$, $(\mathbf{Z}/2\mathbf{Z}) * (\mathbf{Z}/6\mathbf{Z}) * \mathbf{Z}^6$* . Number Theory Listserver, Jun 2006.
- [4] S. Fermigier. *Exemples de Courbes Elliptiques de Grand Rang sur $\mathbf{Q}(t)$ et sur \mathbf{Q} Possedant des points d'ordre 2*. C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris Ser. I **322**(1996), 949–952.
- [5] S. Goldwasser and J. Kilian. *Almost all Primes can be Quickly Certified*. In Proc. 18th STOC, Berkeley, May 28-30, 1986, ACM, New York (1986), 316–329.
- [6] N. Koblitz. *A Course in Number Theory and Cryptography*. Springer-Verlag, 1994.
- [7] T.J. Kretschmer. *Construction of Elliptic Curves with Large Rank*. Math. Comp. **46** (1986), 627–635.
- [8] F. Lemmermeyer and R.A. Mollin. *On the Tate-Shafarevich Groups of $y^2 = x(x^2 - k^2)$* . Acta Math. Universitatis Comenianae **LXXII**(1) (2003), 73–80.
- [9] H.W.Jr. Lenstra. *Factoring Integers with Elliptic Curves*. Annals of Maths. **126**(3) (1987), 649–673.
- [10] R. Martin and W. McMillen. *An Elliptic Curve Over \mathbf{Q} with Rank at least 24*. Number Theory Listserver, May 2000.

- [11] V.S. Miller. *Use of Elliptic Curves in Cryptography*, in *Advances in Cryptology—CRYPTO'85*. Lect. Notes in Comp. Sci. **218**, Springer-Verlag, Berlin (1986), 417–426.
- [12] R.A. Mollin. *An Introduction to Cryptography*. Chapman&Hall/CRC, 2001.
- [13] L.J. Mordell. *On the Rational Solutions of the Indeterminate Eqnarrays of the Third and Fourth Degrees*. Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc. **21**(1922), 179–192.
- [14] U. Schneiders and H.G. Zimmer. *The Rank of Elliptic Curves upon Quadratic Extensions*, in: *Computational Number Theory*. (A. Petho, H.C. Williams, H.G. Zimmer, eds.), de Gruyter, Berlin, 1991.
- [15] R. Schoof. *Counting Points on Elliptic Curves Over Finite Fields*. Journal de Theorie des Nombres de Bordeaux **7**(1995), 219–254.
- [16] A. Tekcan. *The Elliptic Curves $y^2 = x(x-1)(x-\lambda)$* . Accepted by Ars Combinatoria.
- [17] J.H. Silverman. *The Arithmetic of Elliptic Curves*. Springer-Verlag, 1986.
- [18] L.C. Washington. *Elliptic Curves, Number Theory and Cryptography*. Chapman&Hall /CRC, Boca London, New York, Washington DC, 2003.
- [19] A. Wiles. *Modular Elliptic Curves and Fermat's Last Theorem*. Annals of Maths. **141**(3) (1995), 443–551.